

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

*a non-profit
research institute affiliated with
the University of Bergen*

*Edv. Griegsvei 3a,
N-5059 Bergen
Norway*

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DECIDE FOR NEAR-REAL-TIME USE OF OCEAN COLOUR DATA IN MANAGEMENT OF HARMFUL ALGAE BLOOMS

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SATELLITE EO MONITORING OF THE HARMFUL ALGAE BLOOM OF *CHATTONELLA* IN THE NORTH SEA IN APRIL-MAY 2000

in co-operation with

**Centre for Coastal and Marine Sciences-
Plymouth Marine Laboratory
Plymouth, UK**

**Institute of Marine Research
Bergen, Norway**

EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY CONTRACT REPORT

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(version 1.0)**

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Edv. Griegsvei 3a

N-5059 Bergen

NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 29 72 88 Fax: +47 55 20 00 50

e-mail: admin@nrsc.no <http://www.nrsc.no>

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REPORT

TITLE DeciDe for near real-time use of ocean colour data in management of harmful algae blooms. Satellite EO Monitoring of the harmful algae bloom of <i>Chattonella</i> Bloom in the North Sea in April-May 2000	REPORT No. Technical Report no. 199 (version 1.0)
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PROJECT PARTNERS 1. Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway (co-ordinator) 2. Institute of Marine Research, Bergen, Norway.	
REMARK This report is the project deliverable focusing on the definition, design and specifications of a service for applications of EO data in the existing service for HAB monitoring in Norwegian waters.	
APPROVAL Lasse H. Pettersson, project leader	 Ola M. Johannessen, director

Table of Contents

1. BACKGROUND.....	1
2. SUMMARY OF THE DEMONSTRATION PERIOD, APRIL – JUNE 2000.....	2
3. CONCLUSIONS.....	5
4. REFERENCES	5
5. INFORMATION PROVIDED THROUGH THE PROJECT WEB-SITE.....	6

1. Background

A Norwegian service for monitoring of harmful algae blooms (HAB) has been build up, primarily in support of the important aquaculture industry in the coastal waters. This ALGEINFO service is mainly operational during the main bloom season from March to October and publishes weekly its information about the algae bloom situation on a public web-site (<http://algeinfo.imr.no>). During alert bloom situation the information frequency and efforts for monitoring activities are increased, and an operational co-ordination centre is established by the Directorate of Fisheries to perform analysis of the situation, making decisions and disseminating information to the industry, the public and media (e.g as summarised in Pettersson et al., 2000a).

The current monitoring and decision making system for harmful algae bloom situation in Norwegian waters are strongly pending on **early warning** and efficient **monitoring** and **predictions** of the **development and decay** of harmful bloom events. This can only be achieved through an efficient observational system based on an integrated approach using multiple information sources. These information sources includes the current network of 27 coastal stations for *in situ* observations, dedicated ship observations, and under development and evaluation is the use of satellite earth observation (EO) data as well as numerical predictions models for simulations of the bloom evolution (Pettersson et al, 2000b).

The capability of satellite earth observation (EO, i.e. remote sensing) information products (pigment concentration and sea surface temperature) in combination with other observations have proven to be valuable for the early detection and monitoring of (harmful) algae bloom events. However, the limitations of EO data observations with respect to e.g. cloud cover, algae specie discrimination, and subsurface observation capability encourage an integrated implementation strategy where the optimal information are obtained from the various information sources available (Pettersson et al., 2000b).

Activities supported by the Norwegian Space Centre in 1998 demonstrated the first direct applications of SeaWiFS satellite EO data for monitoring of a HAB situation in the Nordic waters. Near-real time SeaWiFS imagery provided an important component in the monitoring of a bloom of *Chattonella aff. verruculosa* in Danish and Norwegian waters during May, 1998.

The main objective of the DeciDe-HAB project is to identify, demonstrate and validate the benefit of using satellite Earth observation (EO) information in support of an existing decision making processes for harmful algae bloom monitoring in Norwegian waters in support of the aquaculture industry. The project specifically addresses the development and implementation of a pre-operational demonstration towards a sustainable service for toxic/harmful algae bloom (HAB) monitoring and management decision support, in which EO data should have an important role.

A more regional approach including EO derived environmental information may contribute achieving an earlier warning, which is necessary for successful mitigation actions. Potential benefits of including use of EO products is also acknowledged for (a) better integration of the regional dimension of HAB events, and (b) potential improvement of regional co-operation with neighbouring countries. The limitations of EO-based monitoring technology such as dependence on cloud-free conditions and inability to detect sub-surface blooms can partly be improved through the integrated use with the current *in situ* based monitoring service. Furthermore, integration EO product with numerical forecasting model (Skogen and Søliland, 1998) has a large potential to improve the quantitative model predictions of development and decay of identified (harmful) bloom situations.

Hence a service based on daily analysis of satellite EO data have been developed, which

disseminate its information through a dedicated web-site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>). The Web-interface provides easy access to daily AVHRR-SST and selected SeaWiFS products, information and analysis of the (H)AB situation. Potential users must register and approved by the project (via the WWW) and their details are entered into a database, which is configured to provided access to only certain areas and products.

This DeciDe-HAB project (Pettersson et al, 2000c) relies on an existing operational satellite data acquisition service performed by the satellite receiving station at the University of Dundee (Scotland) and automatic product generation and dissemination trough the Center for Coastal and Marine Science/Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML). The EO information sources of the HAB monitoring service is based service is based on the daily acquisition of SeaWiFS ocean-colour and NOAA-AVHRR data.

2. Summary of the demonstration period, April – June 2000

A demonstration phase for the evaluation of use of EO data in the HAB monitoring efforts in Norway was implemented for the period April to June 2000. A further demonstration period, with less intensified efforts, was extended until September 2000. During the main project demonstration phase, the Nansen Center has performed interpretation and analysis of around 220 EO images, and derived information products for access via the DeciDe-HAB project web-site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>). A selection of the summary monthly and the daily information and images is included in section 5 of this report.

On April 18., 2000 a significantly increase in the level of chlorophyll pigment concentration in the SeaWiFS data was reported by the Nansen Center to occur along the south west coast of Jutland. This high concentration of algae was confirmed two days later by a routine research cruise of the IMR research vessel G.M. Dannevig to the region. Most of the algae biomass in the region was due to phytoplankton of the class Raphidophyceae. In this class of algae, several harmful species are known, e.g. *Chattonella*, *Fibrocapsa* and *Heterosigma*. On April 20, a tremendously large amount of the algae *Chattonella* aff. *Verruculosa* was reported in the waters west from Esbjerg. The development and decay of the bloom were efficiently monitored using EO and *in situ* data in combination. Due to the development of the algae bloom situation the monitoring operations also went into an alert mode, during this period also satellite data were used to initiate and update the predictions of bloom using the IMR research forecasting algae model (NORWECOM). Clear benefits of using EO data were identified with respect to the planning of the monitoring operations, as well as in the model predictions of the development of the algae bloom. Algae blooms of the same species also occurred in these and in Norwegian coastal waters also in 1998. During these events the algae bloom caused the death of a lot of farmed as well as wild fishes.

During the days prior to May 5 a narrow “thong” of water with higher pigment concentrations was observed to “break out” from the Jutland current into the central and northern parts of Skagerrak. These waters most likely included the *Chattonella* species and could possible cause advection of the blooms to the coastal Norwegian waters. Dedicated field investigations were initiated in order to evaluate this observation. Analysis of the field data confirmed the observations in the satellite image, however these water masses did not reach the Norwegian coastal waters to become a treat for the aquaculture industry.

The Nansen Center, Plymouth Marine Laboratory, the Institute of Marine Research and the Directorate of Fisheries were able to monitor the development and decay of this and other algae blooms using daily updated satellite images, regular, sporadic and dedicated *in situ* measurements and predictive numerical ecosystem model.

Diary of Important Events during the Demonstration Period

Edited extracts from some of the daily analysis reports of the satellite images from the demonstration period follows (prints of the daily web-reports is given in Section 5):

- 12 April - Start of the demonstration period for near real-time EO based monitoring. Establishment of links for downloading of images in near real-time between CCMS-PML and NERSC. Start of daily analysis and interpretations of SeaWiFS and AVHRR images.
- 18 April – In between an extensive cloud cover, increased and very high values of chlorophyll-*a* pigment concentrations were observed in the northern German Bight, around the Sylt area. The observed high pigment concentrations was associated with high reflectance at 555 nm, and low reflectance at 412 nm, which let us presume that the high values could be due to an algae bloom. An alert for a possible algae bloom situation was given to the involved project partners!
- 20 April - The algae bloom detected two days earlier along the western coast of Denmark has moved further off-shore from the near coastal area. The bloom area seems to have increased in spatial coverage, covering a surface area of about 8,000 km². The presence of clouds north of the bloom area, still limits further detailed information. The satellite observations from these two days was later used in a joint effort by the Institute of Marine Research in Bergen to make model predictions of the development and transport of the *Chattonella* bloom. These model simulations were based on their coupled circulation-ecosystem numerical model for the North Sea, and SeaWiFS chlorophyll data as input.
- 21 April - The algae bloom detected on April 18. remains off-shore from the coast and seems to move south-westwards. The presence of clouds north from the bloom area, presently limits further analysis.
- 29 April - The algae bloom identified eleven days ago is in fast expansion. It now covers the entire western coast of Denmark (West Jutland), and extend northwards to Hanstholm. The general spatial extent of the bloom is similar to the *Chattonella* bloom that occurred in 1998 in the same region. The bloom has according to recent field observations been reported to possible *Chattonella* bloom (this bloom will in the text later be referred to as the “*Chattonella* bloom”) and seems presently limited to the west Danish coastal waters and the southern Skagerrak. Its development in the next few days, in relation with the main circulation of the water mass in this region, will be critical in term of an advection towards and possible impact on the Norwegian coast.
- 3 May - The *Chattonella* bloom detected during previous period is still observed along the north coast of Denmark. Another area of high chlorophyll concentration is also observed in the central Skagerrak. Analysis of AVHRR-SST (sea surface temperature) data reveals that the two high-concentration areas pertained to the same water vein. We may thus conclude that the *Chattonella* bloom is currently being advected closer to the Norwegian coast by following seawater meandering in the central Skagerrak.
- 4 May - The *Chattonella* bloom, has extended all way up along the Jutland to the northern point - Skagen. A branch of the waters of high pigment concentrations has also been advected westwards out into the central Skagerrak, westward to 7.0 degr. E at 57.6 degr. N. Analysis of AVHRR-SST (sea surface temperature) data also reveals that the two high-concentration areas pertained to the same water vein.
- 5 May - From analysis of the satellite image, higher chlorophyll pigments concentrations are now observed along the south-coast of Norway (Oslofjorden to Mandal), however the level of the pigment concentration may be partly due to data artefacts. The very high concentration “*Chattonella*” bloom off the Danish west-coast (first detected in the SeaWiFS data of April 18.) has extended all way up along the coast of Jutland to its northern point - Skagen. A branch of the high pigment concentration waters has also been advected westwards out into the central Skagerrak, westward to 7.0 degr. E and 57.6 degr. N. Based on this information the R/V "Munin" of the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries has late on the 5. May made field observations along a section southward from Kristiansand into this area. The field observations confirming high level algae concentrations of various types of flagellates, including *Chattonella*, between 35 - 37 nm off Kristiansand. Analysis of AVHRR-SST (sea surface temperature of May 5. at 14:36 GMT) data also indicates that this high-concentration bloom may origin from the same coastal Danish water masses. The stripes in the image are due to technical problems in the acquisition of the data from the satellite.
- 7 May - Higher level algae pigment concentrations are observed along the Swedish and Norwegian coast westward to Mandal. These high-level pigment concentrations are confined to the very close shore image elements (pixels). Some high-level pigment values are also observed in the Stavanger area and in the Boknafjord (east of Bokn and in Nedstrandsfjorden).

The bloom along west Jutland is still well pronounced extending with a highly visible surface signature (red and yellow colours) from the German Bight to Skagen. lower algae pigment concentrations (green and blue

colours) are observed in eastern Skagerrak, however the peak bloom may be subsurface and not visible in satellite data. Analysis of the AVHRR SST (sea surface temperature) satellite data indicates that the surface waters along the Swedish coast originate from the Kattegatt. The sea surface temperature data also resolve an eddy circulation in the central and as well as out break of the warmer Skagerrak waters along the coast of Jæren.

8 May - The higher level algae pigment concentrations observed along the Swedish and Norwegian coast westward to Mandal, and reported on May 7, are still present. These high-level pigment concentrations are confined to the very close shore image elements (pixels). Some high-level pigment values are also observed in the Stavanger area and in the Boknafjord (east of Bokn and in Nedstrandsfjorden).

The bloom along west Jutland is still well pronounced extending with a highly visible surface signature (red and yellow colours) from the German Bight and almost north to Skagen. However, in the area near Skagen there is observed a slight decrease in the pigment concentrations observed, when compared with yesterday's observations. Lower algae pigment concentrations (green and blue colours) are observed in the eastern Skagerrak, however the peak bloom may be subsurface and not visible in the satellite data. Increasing concentrations are observed in "Jærens rev" (south from Stavanger). Analysis of the AVHRR SST (sea surface temperature) satellite data resolve a warm water eddy circulation in the central Skagerrak and a cold water eddy west of Jæren.

10 May - The higher level algae pigment concentrations observed in the Stavanger area and in the Boknafjord (east of Bokn and in Nedstrandsfjorden), and reported on May 9, are still present. These high values extend to the limit of the monitoring area at 2 deg. West. However, analysis of SeaWiFS products, together with other satellite data does not presently allow us to reach a conclusion on the nature of this feature. An increase in sea surface temperature can be observed in this area in the latest AVHRR-SST available (May 11, 08:30 GMT).

The bloom along west Jutland is still well pronounced extending with a highly visible surface signature (yellow and green colours) from the German Bight and almost north to Skagen. However, pigment concentration is decreasing over the entire area (see Decide image database for time series). Lower algae pigment concentrations (green and blue colours) are observed in the eastern Skagerrak.

13 May - Somewhat higher pigment concentration levels are observed in the entire bloom area of the west Jutland bloom as compared to May 11 and 10. Is the bloom taking up again?. The lower pigment concentrations in central Skagerrak today reaches the area between Skagen and Larvik, most likely associated with inflow of North Sea water into the central Skagerrak (blue colour). Analysing the RGB image ("true colour composite") resolves a brighter surface reflection indicating that a bloom of Coccolitophorids may be under development in this region - i.e. in the water masses of North Sea origin flowing into the Skagerrak region. Higher pigment concentrations (red and yellow colours) is confined to an area (up 5-10 km off shore), except for some further off shore plumes (off Stavanger, Arendal, Kristiansand and Lista), along the coast of south Norway from the Swedish border north to Fedje.

15 May - Decreasing pigment concentration levels are observed in the entire bloom area of the west Jutland bloom as compared to last days. The lower pigment concentrations in central Skagerrak today reaches the area between Skagen and Larvik, most likely associated with inflow of North Sea water into the central Skagerrak (blue colour). Analysing the RGB image ("true color composite") resolves a brighter surface reflection indicating that a bloom of Coccolitophorids may be present in this region - i.e. in the water masses of North Sea origin flowing into the Skagerrak region. Few areas in the northern part of the image) or saturated data.

20 May - The bloom along north Jutland (Jammerbugten) is quite stationary since 15. May. However, a narrow "tongue" of water with lower pigment concentrations (green colour), water of North Sea origin, separates the Danish coastal water from the central Skagerrak water masses. Its signature in low pigments is also observed northward along the Swedish coast. In the central Skagerrak, north and west of the low pigment tongue of North Sea water, the high reflectance signature of Coccolitophorid blooms is dominant (see "true" colour (RGB) image). The higher pigment concentrations are mainly confined to the near shore areas around Skagerrak and Kattegatt. The west Norwegian waters are mainly covered by clouds.

26 May - The bloom along west Jutland has almost collapsed, the remaining high pigment waters are located in the areas in which high sediment concentration influence the value in the satellite data. The high pigment concentration in the Outer Oslofjord is probably associated with flagellate blooms, while the Coccolitophorids dominate the bloom in eastern Skagerrak outside the high pigment concentration area. In between the patchy cloud cover from Skagerrak to the northern part of the mapped area Coccolitophorid blooms are dominating the offshore waters.

31 May - Coccolithophorid blooms dominates the offshore central and northern areas of Skagerrak, except the Swedish coast, Outer Oslofjord and partly the Sørlandskysten. Both the fjords (e.g. Boknafjoren) and offshore areas of the Vestlandet are dominated by coccolits turning the colour of the water "milky-white" (also as confirmed by visual observations). Upwelling situations are observed along Jærkysten and to a minor extent west of Sotra.

The high-level pigment concentrations along the west coast of Jutland are now confined to a near coastal areas, and the high levels most likely from waters dominated by sediments and dissolved organic material. The "*Chattonella* bloom" in this area seems to almost have vanished.

11 June - The northern Skagerrak, the Norwegian Coastal Current and the fjords of southern Norway are still dominated by the Coccolithophorid blooms of *E. Huxleyi*. Some patches are also observed in the central North Sea at around 55 deg. N.

16 June - Chlorophyll concentration tends to decrease in the Skagerrak and along the western coast of Norway. A coccolithophorid bloom is observed in the waters along the western coast of Norway and in the North Sea, where it extends as a very bright pattern in the RGB image

24 June - The coccolithophorid blooms have vanished in the coastal areas, but are still present in the offshore region of the North Sea.

3. Conclusions

The experiences for the HAB's of *Chattonella* in the North Sea region demonstrated, through the development of several algae bloom events, the potential of satellite ocean colour data for early warning of potentially harmful blooming situation. The benefits of synergetic use of EO data with model results and field observations were also demonstrated. It also demonstrated the impact of such an EO integrated service for HAB monitoring at a regional (trans-national) level. During the demonstration phase NERSC received a large number of requests for accessing the password-restricted web site. These requests were sent from different governmental agencies and authorities, research institutions and private companies from Sweden, Denmark, Germany, and other European countries. The R&D nature of the project limited the access to and dissemination of the project information in near real-time.

The integration of the project research activities was good and communications with branch offices of the Fisheries Directorate and the representative of the aquaculture industry was good. The development of the "2000 *Chattonella* bloom" off the Danish Jutland coast and official responses to its monitoring exemplifies the operations, which may be undertaken by the Directorate of Fisheries during the emergency situations caused by HABs.

4. References

Pettersson, Lasse H., Dominique D. Durand, Einar Svendsen, Thomas Noji, Henrik Søiland, Steve Groom, and Sam Lavender, 2000a: DeciDe for near real-time use of ocean colour data in management of harmful algae blooms: Specification, Definition and Design Document NERSC Tech. Report # 186 to ESA under contract no. 13662/99/I-DC. September, 2000.

Pettersson, Lasse H., Dominique D. Durand, Einar Svendsen, Thomas Noji, Henrik Søiland, Steve Groom, 2000b: DeciDe for near real-time use of ocean colour data in management of toxic algae blooms - Analysis Document. NERSC Technical Report no. 180 -B to ESA under contract no. 13662/99/I-DC. May, 2000.

Pettersson, Lasse H., Dominique D. Durand, Einar Svendsen, Thomas Noji, Henrik Søiland, Steve Groom, Samatha Lavender, 2000c: DeciDe for near real-time use of ocean colour data in management of toxic algae blooms – Specification, Definition and Design Document. NERSC Technical Report no. 186 – A to ESA under contract no. 13662/99/I-DC. September, 2000.

Skogen, M. and Søiland, H., 1998. *A user's guide to NORWECOM v2.0, the NORWegian ECOlogical Model system*. Tech. rep. Fisker og Havet, 18. Institute of Marine

5. Information provided through the Project Web-site

On a daily basis the following information were uploaded to a password protected area of the project web-site (<http://www.nrsc.no/Decide-HAB>) from which the information were used to plan further field activities for collection of validation information.

Browsing: /SeaWiFS/2000/04

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SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a products - April 2000

Click on the image for daily interpretation

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to the DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

Wednesday, 12 April 2000 - NEW! HAB info:

Date : 12/4/2000
Product : chlor_a
Satellite : SeaWiFS
Latitude range : 52.000000
61.995018
Longitude range : 2.0000000
12.000000
Slope : 0.015070800
Intercept : 0.010000000
Using climatological ancillary data

Comments :
No HAB detected

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click on the image to see a larger version

Look [here](#) for previous dates.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to the DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

Tuesday, 18 April 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

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Date : 18/4/2000
Product : chlor_a
Satellite : SeaWiFS
Latitude range : 52.000000 61.995018
Longitude range : 2.000000 12.000000
Slope : 0.01124545
Intercept : 0.010000000
Using climatological ancillary data
Valid pixels: 31%

Comments :

Algae bloom detected.

We notice large values of chlorophyll-a in the northern German Bight, around the Sylt area. This is coupled with high [reflectance](#) at 555 nm, and low reflectance at 412 nm, which let us presume that the high values could be due to an algae bloom.

Look [here](#) for previous dates.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to the DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

Thursday, 20 April 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

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Copyright NASA SeaWiFS Project / Orbimage Corp.

Date : 20/4/2000
Product : chlor_a
Satellite : SeaWiFS
Latitude range : 52.000000 61.995018
Longitude range : 2.000000 12.000000
Slope : 0.015070800
Intercept : 0.010000000
Using climatological ancillary data
Valid pixels: 19%

Comments :

The algae bloom detected on Wednesday along the western coast of Denmark has moved away from the coast. The bloom seems to be of a larger extent than before, reaching a surface of about 8,000 km². The presence of clouds north from the bloom area, presently limits further analysis.

In a joint effort, the Institute of Marine Research in Bergen has made [prediction of the development and transport of the *Chattonella* bloom](#) using their coupled circulation-ecosystem numerical model for the North Sea, and SeaWiFS chlorophyll data as input.

Look [here](#) for previous dates.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to the DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

Friday, 21 April 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

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Date : 21/4/2000
Product : chlor_a
Satellite : SeaWiFS
Latitude range : 52.000000 61.995018
Longitude range : 2.000000 12.000000
Slope : 0.015070800
Intercept : 0.010000000
Using climatological ancillary data
Valid pixels: 19%

Comments :

The algae bloom detected on Wednesday along the western coast of Denmark remains away from the coast and seems to move southwestwards. The presence of clouds north from the bloom area, presently limits further analysis.

Look [here](#) for previous dates.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to the DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

Saturday, 29 April 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

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Date : 29/4/2000

Product : chlor_a

Satellite : SeaWiFS

Latitude range : 52.000000 61.995018

Longitude range : 2.0000000 12.000000

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: 65%

Comments :

The algae bloom identified eleven days ago is in fast expansion. It now covers the entire western coast of Denmark (West Jutland), and extend northwards til Hanstholm. The general extent of the bloom is very similar to the *Chattonella* bloom that occurred in 1998 in the same region. The bloom, which is probably a new *Chattonella* bloom according to recent field observations, seems presently constraint to the danish coast and south Skagerrak. Its development in the next few days, in relation with the main water mass circulation in this region, will be critical in term of a possible impact on the Nowergian coast .

Look [here](#) for previous dates.

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Browsing: /SeaWiFS/2000/05

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SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a products - May 2000

Click on the image for daily interpretation

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Wednesday, 03 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Copyright NASA SeaWiFS Project / Orbimage Corp.

Date : 03/5/2000

Product : chlor_a

Satellite : SeaWiFS

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: 37%

Comments :

The *Chattonella* bloom detected the previous days is still observed along the north coast of Denmark. Another area of high chlorophyll concentration is also observed in the center Skagerrak. Analysis of AVHRR-SST (sea surface temperature) data reveals that the two high-concentration areas pertained to the same water vein. We can thus conclude that the *Chattonella* bloom is currently coming closer to the coast of Norway by following sea-water meanders in the Skagerrak. .

Look [here](#) for previous dates.

This Web-site is maintained by [Dominique Durand](#), NERSC

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Thursday, 04 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Date : 04/5/2000

Product : chlor_a

Satellite : SeaWiFS

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

The *Chattonella* bloom first detected in the SeaWiFS data of April 18. off the west coast of Denmark, has extended all way up along the Jutland to the northern point - Skagen. A branch of the waters of high pigment concentrations has also been advected westwards out into the central Skagerrak, westward to 7.0 degr. E at 57.6 degr. N. Analysis of [AVHRR-SST](#) (sea surface temperature) data also reveals that the two high-concentration areas pertained to the same water vein. .

Look [here](#) for previous dates.

This Web-site is maintained by [Dominique Durand](#), NERSC

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Friday, 05 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Copyright NASA SeaWiFS Project / Orbimage Corp.

Date : 05/5/2000

Product : chlor_a

Satellite : SeaWiFS

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

From interpretations of the satellite image higher chlorophyll pigments concentrations are now observed along the south-coast of Norway (Oslofjorden to Mandal), however the level of the pigment concentration may be partly due to data artefacts.

The very high concentration bloom off the west-coast of Denmark (first detected in the SeaWiFS data of April 18.) has extended all way up along the coast of Jutland to its northern point - Skagen. A branch of the high pigment concentration waters has also been advected westwards out into the central Skagerrak, westward to 7.0 degr. E and 57.6 degr. N. Based on this information the R/V "Munin" of the Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries has late on the 5. May made field observations along a section from Kristiansand into this area, confirming high level algae concentrations of various types of flagellates between 35 - 37 nm off Kristiansand. Analysis of [AVHRR-SST](#) (sea surface temperature of May 5. at 14:36 GMT) data also indicates that this high-concentration bloom may origin from the same coastal Danish water masses.

The stripes in the image are due to technical problems in the acquisition of the data from the satellite.

..

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Sunday, 07 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Copyright NASA SeaWiFS Project / Orbimage Corp.

Date : 07/5/2000

Product : chlor_a

Satellite : SeaWiFS

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

Higher level algae pigment concentrations are observed along the Swedish and Norwegian coast westward to Mandal. These high-level pigment concentrations are confined to the very close shore image elements (pixels). Some high-level pigment values are also observed in the Stavanger area and in the Boknafjord (east of Bokn and in Nedstrandsfjorden).

The bloom along west Jutland is still well pronounced extending with a highly visible surface signature (red and yellow colours) from the German Bight to Skagen. Slightly lower algae pigment concentrations (green and blue colours) are observed in the eastern Skagerrak, however the peak bloom may be subsurface and not visible in the satellite data. Analysis of the [AVHRR SST](#) (sea surface temperature) satellite data indicates that the surface waters along the Swedish coast origins from the Kategatt. The sea surface temperature data also resolve an eddy circulation in the central Skagerrak and as well as out break of the warmer Skagerrak waters along the coast of Jaeren.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Monday, 08 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Evaluation of the situation as of: 08/5/2000

Product : SeaWiFS chlor_a

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

The higher level algae pigment concentrations observed along the Swedish and Norwegian coast westward to Mandal, and reported on May 7, are still present. These high-level pigment concentrations are confined to the very close shore image elements (pixels). Some high-level pigment values are also observed in the Stavanger area and in the Boknafjord (east of Bokn and in Nedstrandsfjorden). The bloom along west Jutland is still well pronounced extending with a highly visible surface signature (red and yellow colours) from the German Bight and almost north to Skagen.

However, in the area near Skagen there is observed a slight decrease in the pigment concentrations observed when comparing with [yesterday's observations](#).

Lower algae pigment concentrations (green and blue colours) are observed in the eastern Skagerrak, however the peak bloom may be subsurface and not visible in the satellite data. Increasing concentrations are observed in "Jaerens rev" (south from Stavanger). Analysis of the [AVHRR SST](#) (sea surface temperature) satellite data resolve a warm water eddy circulation in the central Skagerrak and a cold water eddy west of Jaeren.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Tuesday, 09 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Evaluation of the situation as of: 09/5/2000

Product : SeaWiFS chlor_a

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

The higher level algae pigment concentrations observed along the Swedish and Norwegian coast westward to Mandal, and reported on May 7, are still present. These high-level pigment concentrations are confined to the very close shore image elements (pixels). Some high-level pigment values are also observed in the Stavanger area and in the Boknafjord (east of Bokn and in Nedstrandsfjorden). The bloom along west Jutland is still well pronounced extending with a highly visible surface signature (red and yellow colours) from the German Bight and almost north to Skagen.

However, in the area near Skagen, pigment concentrations are still decreasing (see [Decide image database for the month of May](#)).

Lower algae pigment concentrations (green and blue colours) are observed in the eastern Skagerrak, however the peak bloom may be subsurface and not visible in the satellite data. Increasing concentrations are observed in "Jaerens rev" (south from Stavanger). Analysis of the [AVHRR SST](#) (sea surface temperature) satellite data resolve a warm water eddy circulation in the central Skagerrak and a cold water eddy west of Jaeren.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Wednesday, 10 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Evaluation of the situation as of: 10/5/2000

Product : SeaWiFS chlor_a

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

The higher level algae pigment concentrations observed in the Stavanger area and in the Boknafjord (east of Bokn and in Nedstrandsfjorden), and reported on May 9, are still present. These high values extend to the limit of the monitoring area at 2 deg. West. However, analysis of SeaWiFS products, together with other satellite data does not presently allow us to reach a conclusion on the nature of this feature. An increase in sea surface temperature can be observed in this area in the latest [AVHRR-SST](#) image available (May 11, 08.30 AM).

The bloom along west Jutland is still well pronounced extending with a highly visible surface signature (yellow and green colours) from the German Bight and almost north to Skagen. **However, pigment concentration is decreasing over the entire area** (see [Decide image database for time series](#)) .

Lower algae pigment concentrations (green and blue colours) are observed in the eastern Skagerrak.

Analysis of the [AVHRR SST](#) (sea surface temperature) satellite data resolve a warm water eddy circulation in the central Skagerrak and a cold water eddy west of Jaeren.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Saturday, 13 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Evaluation of the situation as of: 13/5/2000

Product : SeaWiFS chlor_a

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

Somewhat higher pigment concentration levels are observed in the entire bloom area of the west Jutland bloom as compared to May 11 and 10. Is the bloom taking up again?. The lower pigment concentrations in central Skagerrak today reaches the area between Skagen and Larvik, most likely associated with inflow of North Sea water into the central Skagerrak (blue color). Higher pigment concentrations (red and yellow colors) is confined to an area (up 5-10 km off shore), except for some further off shore plumes (off Stavanger, Arendal, Kristiansand and Lista), along the coast of south Norway from the Swedish border north to Fedje. The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds (only a few areas in the northern part of the image) or saturated data.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Monday, 15 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Evaluation of the situation as of: 15/5/2000

Product : SeaWiFS chlor_a

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

Decreasing pigment concentration levels are observed in the entire bloom area of the west Jutland bloom as compared to last days. The lower pigment concentrations in central Skagerrak today reaches the area between Skagen and Larvik, most likely associated with inflow of North Sea water into the central Skagerrak (blue color). Analyzing the [RGB image](#) ("true color composite") resolves a brighter surface reflection indicating that a bloom of Coccolithophorids may be present in this region - i.e. in the water masses of North Sea origin flowing into the Skagerrak region. few areas in the northern part of the image) or saturated data. The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

In a joint effort, the Institute of Marine Research in Bergen has made [prediction of the development and transport of the *Chattonella* bloom](#) using their coupled circulation-ecosystem numerical model for the North Sea, and SeaWiFS chlorophyll data as input.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Saturday, 20 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Evaluation of the situation as of: 20/5/2000

Product : SeaWiFS chlor_a

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Valid pixels: %

Comments :

The bloom along north Jutland (Jammerbugten) is quite stationary since 15. May. However, a narrow "tongue" of water with lower pigment concentrations (green color), water of North Sea origin, separates the Danish coastal water from the central Skagerrak water masses. Its signature in low pigments is also observed northward along the Swedish coast. In the central Skagerrak, north and west of the low pigment tongue of North Sea water, the high reflectance signature of Coccolitophorid blooms is dominant (see ["true" color \(RGB\) image](#)).

The higher pigment concentrations are mainly confined to the near shore areas around Skagerrak and Kategatt. West Norway is covered mainly by clouds.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

In a joint effort, the Institute of Marine Research in Bergen has made [prediction of the development and transport of the *Chattonella* bloom](#) using their coupled circulation-ecosystem numerical model for the North Sea, and SeaWiFS chlorophyll data as input.

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DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Friday, 26 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

Evaluation of the situation as of: 26/5/2000

Products : SeaWiFS chlor_a (left) and RGB reflectance composite (right)

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N
Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W
Using climatological ancillary data

Comments :

The bloom along west Jutland has almost collapsed, the remaining high pigment waters are located in the areas in which high sediment concentrations influence the value in the satellite data. The high pigment concentrations in the Outer Oslofjord is probably associated with flagellate blooms, while the Coccolithophorids dominates the bloom in eastern Skagerrak outside the high pigment concentration area. In between the patchy cloud cover from Skagearrak to the northern part of the mapped area Coccolithophorid blooms are dominating the off-shore waters.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Wednesday, 31 May 2000 - NEW! HAB info

Evaluation of the situation as of: 31/5/2000

Products : SeaWiFS chlor_a (left) and RGB reflectance composite (right)

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N
Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W
 Using climatological ancillary data

Comments :

Coccolithophorid blooms dominates the off-shore central and northern areas of Skagerrak, except the Swedish coast, Outer Oslofjord and partly the Sorlandskysten. Both the fjords (e.g. Boknafjoren) and offshore areas of the Vestlandet is dominated by coccoliths turning the water color "milky-white". Upwelling situations are observed along Jaerkysetn and to a minor extent west of Sotra. The high level pigment concentrations along the west coast of Jutland are now confined to a near coastal areas, and the high levels most likely from waters dominated by sediments and dissolved organic material.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Browsing: /SeaWiFS/2000/06

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SeaWiFS chlorophyll-a products - June 2000

Click on the image for daily interpretation

01 June 2000 No Image Available	02 June 2000 						
09 June 2000 							
17 June 2000 							
25 June 2000 (Image)							

DeciDe for Near Real-Time Use of Ocean Colour Data in Management of Toxic Algae Blooms

Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Saturday, 03 June 2000 - NEW! HAB info

Evaluation of the situation as of:

03/6/2000

Products : SeaWiFS chlor_a (left) and

RGB reflectance composite (right)

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Comments :

Coccolithophorid blooms dominates the off-shore central and northern areas of Skagerrak, except the Swedish coast, Outer Oslofjord and partly the Sorlandskysten. Both the fjords (e.g. Boknafjoren) and offshore areas of the Vestlandet is dominated by coccoliths turning the water color "milky-white".

The chlorophyll concentration map (on the left) displays similar patterns as the ones observed in the SST products along the northern coast of Denmark and in the Kattegatt. High concentration values are observed in the warm water tongue crossing the Kattegatt towards the coast of Sweden. This is potentially a blooming situation, even if it can not be yet confirmed by the analysis of the reflectance RGB composite (on the right).

Upwelling situations are observed along Jaerkysetn and to a minor extent west of Sotra. The high level pigment concentrations along the west coast of Jutland are now confined to a near coastal areas, and the high levels most likely from waters dominated by sediments and dissolved organic material.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Friday, 09 June 2000 - NEW! HAB info

Evaluation of the situation as of: 09/6/2000

Products : SeaWiFS chlor_a (left) and RGB reflectance composite (right)

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Comments :

The northern Skagerrak, the Norwegian Coastal Current and the fjords of southern Norway are still dominated by the Coccolitophorid blooms of *E. Huxleyi*. However *E. Huxleyi* seems to be mixed with other types of algae in the northern Skagerrak (brown area over the bright one in the RGB image on the right), resulting in very high chlorophyll concentration along the coast of Sweden, Oslofjorden and the southern coast of Norway.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Friday, 16 June 2000 - NEW! HAB info

Evaluation of the situation as of: 16/6/2000

Products : SeaWiFS chlor_a (left) and RGB reflectance composite (right)

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Comments :

Chlorophyll concentration tends to decrease in the Skagerrak and along the west coast of Norway. A coccolithophorid bloom is nevertheless observed along the western coast of Norway and in the North Sea, where it extends as a very bright horizontal pattern in the RGB image (on the right).

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

click on the image to enlarge

Land and clouds in black

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Welcome to DeciDe's daily image from the North-Sea/Skagerrak

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Saturday, 24 June 2000 - NEW! HAB info

Chlorophyll concentration
Land in black, clouds and unvalid pixels in white

RGB composite

Evaluation of the situation as of:

24/6/2000

Products : SeaWiFS chlor_a (left) and RGB reflectance composite (right)

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Comments :

The coccolithophorid blooms have vanished in the coastal areas, but are still present in the offshore region of the North Sea.

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

click on the image to enlarge

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Thursday, 29 June 2000 - NEW! HAB info

Chlorophyll concentration
Land in black, clouds and unvalid pixels in white

RGB composite

Evaluation of the situation as of:
29/6/2000

Products : SeaWiFS chlor_a (left) and

RGB reflectance composite (right)

Latitude range : 52.0 62.0 N

Longitude range : 2.0 12.0 W

Using climatological ancillary data

Comments :

The low algae pigment concentration waters of the central North Sea is indicated in purple colours. Black colour: Land, clouds or saturated data.

click on the image to enlarge

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